

PID to Portal

Deliverable A1
Framework report

PID to Portal
Deliverable A1: Framework

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Contact:

Maurice Vanderfeesten

maurice.vanderfeesten@surf.nl

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6397-4759>

Report author:

Bianca Kramer (Sesame Open Science)

bianca@sesameopenscience.org

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5965-6560>

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BACKGROUND

The visibility, quality, and reliability of Dutch research information are increasingly vital for national and international collaboration, open science policies, and institutional steering. This project strengthens the infrastructure for Open Research Information (ORI), enabling Dutch institutions to maintain control over their research outputs while aligning with key developments such as the NPOS ambitions and the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information.

Current gaps in metadata quality, persistent identifier (PID) usage, and system integration hinder both policy compliance and strategic insight. At the same time, there is a growing dependence on external platforms, and an opportunity to both analyze and address metadata quality and PID usage and interoperability in ways that closed infrastructures do not allow.

The PID to Portal project aims to develop a monitoring framework and ORI-related measurements that provide actionable insights into metadata quality, PID adoption, and metadata licensing across institutions. The project will monitor the quality and coverage of PIDs and metadata, and will define possible interventions and priorities to improve those at the source. This prologues the activities in OSNL projects DURF and BROCCOLI.

This report (Deliverable A1) describes a set of prioritized use cases, metadata elements, sources, aspects of metadata quality and expected issues, using insights from a consultation session with NL Barcelona Declaration Signatories. Building on these insights, a high-level overview of the monitoring framework is provided. By comparing prioritized metadata elements across sources, gaps in metadata coverage can be identified. This will inform interventions to improve metadata coverage and quality in relevant sources, which in turn will benefit common use cases.

A follow-up report (Deliverable A2) will outline detailed metrics of quality & coverage of prioritized entities (PIDs and other metadata), documenting what and how to measure for each type of metadata element.

REQUIREMENTS

To decide what metadata elements and what aspects of metadata quality to give priority, the project employs a use-case driven approach, focusing on those use cases where open, reliable and complete metadata have the most value for Dutch research institutions.

Since organizations that signed the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information¹ made an explicit commitment to enable, improve and support open research information, the group of Dutch signatories and prospective signatories to the Declaration², was invited to contribute their most important use cases, including the most relevant metadata elements for these use cases. The survey questions used to solicit use cases are included in Appendix 1.

In a follow-up meeting, the use cases and prioritized metadata elements were discussed, as well as how this group conceptualized metadata quality and what issues they expected regarding quality of open metadata.

Use cases

Participants were asked to contribute one or more use cases for open research information on Dutch research output, and categorize their use case using the classification proposed in UNL's Open Research Information Agenda (2023)³:

- Reporting
- Evaluation and assessment
- Analysis
- Archiving, storage and sharing
- Information and dissemination

A more detailed description of these categories can be found in the 2023 ORIA report³.

Use cases - grouping and relevance

In total, 14 use cases were submitted from 10 organizations, including universities, NWO and UKB/SURF (Table 1). Use cases were submitted from various roles within the organization, including library management, open science support, CRIS management, research support and policy advice. Since organizations submitted use cases independently, in the in-person meeting the relevance of each use for other organizations was inventorized.

Multiple use cases were mentioned around open access monitoring (A-B) and filling of CRIS systems (C-F). Another group of use cases (G-H) centered on linking data from various sources, including implementation of PIDs. Then, there was a group of individual use cases (I-M) centered around generating various types of information for faculty and library processes (research profiles, benchmarking, collection development, researcher assessment

¹<https://barcelona-declaration.org>

²https://barcelona-declaration.org/national_networks/

³<https://www.universiteitenvannederland.nl/files/publications/Open%20Research%20Information%20Agenda%20%28Businesscase%20OKB%29.pdf>

and mapping research collaborations). Finally, one use case (N) centered on collection of specific information (corresponding authors) needed for other types of analysis. Detailed information on each submitted use case is available in Appendix 2.

Most use cases were recognized as relevant by half or more of the institutions participating in the consultation meeting (Table 1), with the exception of two individual use cases on benchmarking funding acquisition (use case I) and finding alternatives for impact factors (use case K). Two use cases (F and M) were submitted after the consultation meeting, and thus could not be assessed this way.

The three use cases that were relevant for most institutions were those around **monitoring open access** (use cases A/B), **linking data from multiple sources (including PIDs)** (use cases G/H) and **identifying corresponding authors** (use case N).

Table 1. Use cases for open metadata for Dutch research output. Use cases submitted by Dutch (prospective) signatories to the Barcelona Declaration. Relevance of use cases for other institutions was inventorized in the in-person consultation meeting, where 8 institutions were represented.

Use case	Description	Relevance
A	Automated, reproducible and correct open access monitor based on open metadata	6/8
B	Open Access monitoring based on open metadata	
C	Using open research information to fill our CRIS system	
D	Bulk import of research output into CRIS	4/8
E	Bulk Import of datasets into CRIS	
F	Populating CRIS with institution's article output	
G	Linking data from multiple sources	6/8
H	Implementing a mature PID strategy	
I	Providing insights to faculties about their research publication profile	5/8
J	Benchmark university's performance in acquiring 2nd and 3rd funding streams	1/8
K	Collection evaluation by integrating deal information with OA status and APC costs	4/8
L	Providing alternatives for JCR, specifically for author impact profiles	3/8
M	Mapping research collaborations	NA
N	Availability of corresponding author information	7/8

Categories

The submitted use cases mostly fell into the categories 'Reporting', 'Assessment and Evaluation' and 'Analysis' (Table 2). The other ORIA-categories (Archiving, storage and sharing' and 'Information and dissemination' were only mentioned by 3 use cases, on filling CRIS and implementing PID strategies, respectively. Only one use case (F) submitted a category as 'Other', namely 'Registering'.

It should be noted that use cases were self-assigned to categories by submitting institutions, and there was a certain degree of variance in the categories similar use cases were assigned to. This could reflect institutional differences in interpretation of the categories.

Notwithstanding this variance, it seems clear that institutions are looking to use open research information primarily for reporting, assessment and evaluation and analysis.

Table 2. Categorization of use cases. Categories as per the UNL Open Research Information Agenda³.

Category	Use cases													
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
Reporting	●	●	●	●			●	●	●					●
Assessment / evaluation	●	●	●		●		●	●				●		●
Analysis	●	●		●			●			●	●		●	●
Archiving / sharing				●	●			●						
Information / dissemination				●	●			●						

Similar use cases

Prior to this inventorization of use cases for open research information, a similar initiative was started by Jeroen Bosman (UU) and Matthijs de Zwaan (VU) for the Research Intelligence Network Netherlands (RINN)⁴. The RINN inventorization is aimed at collecting and characterizing use cases for Web of Science and Scopus, with the aim of exploring the opportunities and barriers for transitioning to open systems of research information.

While the RINN initiative uses a slightly different lens (use cases for closed systems, and not limited to research output from Dutch institutions), there is a large degree of overlap between both sets of use cases (see Figure 1) with the use cases collected for the PID to Portal project all covered by the somewhat broader use cases of the RINN project. The RINN project

⁴ [Use cases for Scopus and WoS in the Netherlands \(for RINN\)](#)

includes some additional use cases that fall outside the scope of the PID to Portal project, namely those around finding information (by or for researchers) and doing metascience (including information on research output from non-Dutch institutions).

Figure 1. Comparison with use cases for Scopus/WoS collected for RINN. Use cases collected for the PID to Portal project (left) and those collected for RINN (right). Purple use cases indicate RINN use cases that correspond to one or more PID to Portal use cases.

Metadata elements

As part of the survey, institutions were asked to indicate which metadata elements were relevant for the use case(s) they had submitted (Table 3). Across use cases, **DOIs**, **institutional identifiers/RORs** and **ORCIDs** were mentioned most frequently - each of these was deemed relevant for half or more of our use cases. A second set of metadata elements was mentioned in association with 2-4 use cases (ISSN, OA status, Corresponding author, ISBN, Grant DOI). Finally, some metadata elements were mentioned for one specific use case only (internal Grant IDs, APC costs, deal information, citations, journal citations, RAID).

It should be kept in mind that there is a degree of subjectivity in the assessment of relevant metadata - both in what is deemed relevant and what is deemed to be metadata. For example, for one of the two use cases around Open Access monitoring, 'OA status' was provided as an answer, while for the other use case, it was not.

Only DOIs were mentioned as PIDs for research outputs (articles, datasets etc), but this category could be extended to other identifiers, such as Handles.

In using these answers to prioritize relevant metadata, the extent to which use cases are relevant across institutions should also be kept in mind. Taking into account that use cases around monitoring open access (A/B), linking data from multiple sources (including PIDs) (G/H) and identifying corresponding authors (N) were shared by over half of institutions, two other relevant metadata elements (in addition to DOIs, Institutional identifiers/RORs and ORCIDs) could be considered to be **corresponding authors** and **OA status**. To serve specific use cases, **ISSNs** and **Grant DOIs** could also be considered for inclusion in the monitoring framework.

Table 3. Metadata elements relevant for use cases. Metadata elements mentioned for at least two use cases, as free-text answers.

Metadata elements	Use cases													
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N
DOIs	●	●	●	●		●	●	●	●	●	●		●	
Institutional identifier / ROR				●	●	●	●	●	●	●			●	
ORCID		●		●	●	●	●	●						
ISSN				●		●			●		●			
OA status	●										●			
Corresponding author											●			●
ISBN				●					●					
Grant DOI									●	●				

Sources

A number of different sources of research information were mentioned in association with the various use cases. These can be divided into internal and external systems and among the latter, open and closed systems⁵ (for internal systems, institutions themselves are in control of the extent to which the data in these systems is made openly available). In addition, in some cases a differentiation can be made between systems currently in use and the (open)

⁵ For internal systems, institutions themselves are in control of the extent to which the data in these systems is made openly available, depending on internal policies, technical implementation and terms negotiated with system providers.

systems that institutions would like to transition towards. Table 4 shows all systems mentioned in the survey.

Table 4. Sources relevant for use cases. Sources mentioned in description of workflows for each use case. For detailed information per use case see Appendix 2.

Sources			
	current use		prospective use
internal systems	external systems (closed)	external systems (open)	external systems (open)
CRIS	Web of Science	OpenAlex	OpenAlex
ISAAC	Scopus	OpenAIRE	OpenAIRE
MyZonMw	Altmetric	Crossref	Crossref
UKBsis	Overton	Unpaywall	
Learning Management System	Publisher reports	DOAJ	
Contract Management Database		PubMed	
Journal software		CORDIS	
		NWO	

From these data, it is apparent that a variety of systems, both open and closed, is currently being used. Among internal systems, CRIS (including the equivalents at NWO and ZonMw) are most often mentioned. Among external closed systems, unsurprisingly Web of Science and Scopus are most often mentioned, with their counterparts OpenAlex and OpenAIRE mentioned as open systems in use by multiple institutions. Other open systems mentioned multiple times are Crossref (as primary source of metadata) and Unpaywall (for OA information). Interestingly, OpenAlex, OpenAIRE and Crossref are also mentioned as systems institutions are interested in, but not currently using.

From these data, it seems justified to consider **OpenAlex**, **OpenAIRE** and **Crossref** as the most logical candidates to include in the monitoring framework. For institutional output, a comparison with internal data in the **CRIS** would be useful for validation of both the CRIS themselves and external open sources.

Quality aspects

When assessing the quality of metadata for institutional use cases, different aspects may be considered more or less important. Survey respondents were asked to indicate which quality aspects were important for the use case(s) they submitted. The survey offered a number of preselected options: completeness, accuracy, being up-to-date and openness, as well as the

option to provide free text answers. Metadata quality aspects were correlated to the metadata elements deemed relevant for each respective use case (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Metadata quality aspects. Gradient shows the percentage of use cases (per metadata element) for which each quality aspect was mentioned as relevant. Metadata elements mentioned in at least two use cases are included.

These data show that for most metadata elements, **accuracy, completeness** and, to a somewhat lesser extent, **being up-to-date** are seen as most relevant. Specifically for the three metadata types (DOIs, institutional identifiers/RORs and ORCIDs) previously identified as relevant for most use cases, **openness** also is deemed an important quality.

Even though there appears to be broad consensus around the relative importance of these metadata quality aspects, there is room for different interpretations on what they mean in practice (and thus, how they should be monitored). This was further discussed in the consultation meeting.

The following operationalizations of 'quality' were proposed for each metadata aspect, with the understanding that these are non-exclusive, meaning that multiple operationalizations can be relevant for each quality aspect.

Table 5. Operationalizations of metadata quality. As discussed at the consultation meeting.

Quality aspect	Operationalization
Accuracy	Agreement with 'authoritative source' (and agreement on what that source would be)
	Agreement between sources (taking into account feedback loops)
	Indication of provenance
	Transparent processes (e.g. for ID assignment, harmonization)
Completeness	Presence of metadata for each record (e.g. affiliation data for each article)
	Presence of metadata for each entity within a record (e.g. ORCID for all authors)
	Presence of all metadata subfields (e.g. raw affiliation string and ROR for affiliations)
Being up-to-date	Information being current (e.g. OA information)
	Transparency on last update per metadata field (esp. OA information)
	Availability of regular data snapshots
Openness	Open license on metadata (CC0, CC BY?)
	Full data downloads (JSON / CSV)
	API with access to all fields, no access restrictions
	User interface with access to all fields

Discussions during the consultation meeting did not result in clear consensus on any one operationalization as most relevant - in contrast, it was recognized that most aspects proposed were considered relevant. Nonetheless, making these aspects explicit as operationalizations - combined with an assessment of the feasibility of assessing them in various sources, can help in deciding what choices to make in the monitoring of metadata quality.

Of these metadata quality aspects, openness can be considered both a quality of the metadata itself (metadata license) and of the infrastructure providing the metadata (database license, download options, API, user interface).

Expected issues

Finally, survey participants were asked, for each use case, where the availability of open metadata is currently limited, and data quality of open metadata is currently perceived or expected to be a problem (Table 6).

This information can be used both to decide on specific aspects of metadata coverage and completeness to include in monitoring, and, if and when confirmed, where to target interventions.

Table 6. Perceived limitations and issues of open research information. Limitations and issues identified by survey participants for the various use cases submitted.

Metadata element	Description of limitation(s) / issue(s)
Affiliation metadata	Not fine-grained enough, lack of curation/harmonization, incomplete
Author identifiers	Incomplete, limited quality, disambiguation, Scopus is pushing Scopus author ID
Citations	Incomplete; lack of normalized citation indicators (FWCI or CNCI)
Corresponding author status	More complete in Scopus than OpenAlex; missing in OpenAIRE
Funding metadata	Manual classification of grants into (sub) programmes needed
Funding metadata	Not complete; i.e. awarded euros per project
Funding/project metadata	Not updated; projects IDs changed, change in project participants
ISSNs	Incomplete, lack of harmonization (also a problem with closed sources)
Journal	Potentially too strict definition of what is a journal
OA status	Too often incorrect in Unpaywallt (esp for repository OA)
PIDs	Missing (e.g. DOIs, RORs, grant DOIs/ID)
Subject classification	Not fine-grained enough; "only 4,500 distinct topics"
General	No process to prevent data pollution

FRAMEWORK

The monitoring framework builds on the inventorization of prioritized use cases, metadata elements, sources, aspects of metadata quality and expected issues. By comparing prioritized metadata elements across sources, gaps in metadata coverage can be identified. This will inform interventions to improve metadata coverage and quality in relevant sources, which in turn will benefit common use cases.

Entities

Sources

To best support the prioritized use cases of institutions (**monitoring open access, linking data from multiple sources (including PIDs)**, and **identifying corresponding authors**), the monitoring will focus on **OpenAlex** and **OpenAIRE** as external sources of open research information, supplemented by **Crossref**.

Since many use cases also make use of institutions' own CRIS as source, or are aimed at filling and enriching the CRIS, it will be useful to also include the **CRIS** as source for the monitoring framework - either directly (with data supplied by institutions) or indirectly (with raw harvested CRIS data supplied by OpenAIRE). By including CRIS data, the PID to Portal project will also feed more directly into the OSNL projects DURF and BROCCOLI.

For Universities of Applied Sciences, it might be relevant to consider looking at Kennisbank HBO and/or PubliNova as sources of publications and other (research) output - again, either directly or, for HBO Kennisbank via raw harvested data supplied by OpenAIRE. Some, but not all Universities of Applied Sciences also have their own CRIS.

Metadata elements

Based on the inventorization of use cases and associated relevant metadata, the monitoring framework will, in its first iteration, focus on **DOIs**, **institutional identifiers/RORs** and **ORCIDs** as core metadata elements. In a second iteration, **corresponding author status** and **OA status** can be considered. Other metadata elements of interest for specific use cases are **ISSNs** (for journal level analysis) and **Grant DOIs**.

Although in the use cases, only DOIs were mentioned as PIDs for research outputs (articles, datasets etc), this category could be extended to other identifiers, such as Handles.

Two metadata elements (DOIs and institutional identifiers/RORs) can be used to create specific subsets of research outputs from the various sources. To support the filtering of research outputs, additional metadata elements to take into account could be **publication type**, **subject classification** and **publication year**. It should be noted that these latter metadata elements often are treated differently in different sources (e.g. using different definitions and classifications). Therefore, they might themselves need to be subject to comparison as well.

While many use cases focus on research outputs as the main entity, a similar approach can be taken to look at subsets of e.g. researchers or journals, by filtering on ORCID IDs and ISSN numbers, respectively.

Gaps

Comparison across sources

Once a specific subset is identified (e.g. journal articles from a specific university for a specific year), a comparison can be made on the quality of specific metadata elements for this set of outputs across different sources. This can include the metadata used to create the subset itself (e.g. journal articles having a specific affiliation in one source, but not in another source) to compare coverage in and retrieval from multiple sources.

Depending on the use case in mind, comparison can focus on **accuracy** (agreement with 'authoritative source', agreement between sources, indication of provenance), **completeness** (presence of metadata for each record, presence of metadata for each entity within a record and/or presence of all metadata subfields), **being up-to-date** (information being current, transparency on last update per metadata field) and **openness** (open license on metadata).

It should be noted that some aspects of metadata quality are at the level of the source/database as a whole, rather than on the level of individual metadata fields, and thus would need to be assessed separately. These include aspects of **accuracy** (transparent processes for e.g. ID assignment and harmonization), **being up to date** (availability of regular data snapshots) and **openness** (open license on database, full data downloads, no access restrictions, API with access to all fields, user interface with access to all fields).

Figure 3 provides a schematic overview of the monitoring framework, using the example of comparing affiliation metadata for a set of journal articles (with DOI) from one institution, with examples of metadata quality aspects that can be assessed across data sources.

Identifying gaps

The goal of this comparison is to reveal differences (**delta's**) in metadata quality aspects between data sources, and subsequently, investigate where **gaps** exist in any specific data source.

For instance, if subsets of articles are retrieved by ROR in database A but not database B, is this due to: lack of affiliation data altogether, lack of affiliation data for specific articles (e.g. from certain publishers) or incomplete matching of affiliation strings to ROR in database B, or incorrect affiliation assignment in database A?

Figure 3. Monitoring framework. Schematic representation of comparing metadata quality (here: affiliation metadata for a subset of journal articles) in different databases. Examples are given of aspects of metadata that can be assessed. Purple triangles indicate (potential) differences (delta) between datasources for these aspects. .

Interventions

Identifying gaps in metadata quality can inform **interventions** to improve metadata quality in upstream sources of open research information, which in turn will improve data quality for the various use cases relevant to Dutch institutions.

The nature of potential interventions will depend on the nature of the identified gaps. For example, if affiliation metadata (including RORs) for Dutch research output is missing in Crossref for specific publishers, this can be taken up with the publisher, including in publisher negotiations. If OpenAlex or OpenAIRE do not assign correct affiliation metadata (e.g. by not matching certain affiliation strings to ROR, or making incorrect matches), this can be taken up with them, providing concrete examples or even full datasets for troubleshooting. If institutions' own CRIS lack research outputs that are (correctly) identified in other systems as affiliated to the institution in other systems, this could lead to optimization of internal systems to fill such gaps.

The goal of the PID to Portal project is to develop and operationalize a framework to identify gaps in metadata quality in various sources of open research information in order to inform a discussion on potential interventions to remedy such gaps. Priority will be given to the sources and metadata elements that are relevant for common use cases of open research information on Dutch research output, as identified by Dutch research performing and funding organizations.

A follow-up report (Deliverable A2) will outline detailed metrics of metadata quality aspects of prioritized entities (PIDs and other metadata), documenting what can be measured for each type of metadata element.

APPENDIX 1 - SURVEY QUESTIONS

PID-to-Portal workshop pre-survey

Use cases NL Barcelona Declaration network

Section 1 - About this survey

With this survey, we want to collect concrete use cases for open research information from NL research performing and funding organizations. The goal is to inform the PID-to-Portal project, in particular the development of a monitor for the quality and completeness of open research information for the Dutch research ecosystem.

This monitoring should help research organizations with:

- improving metadata quality and coverage in relevant sources (e.g., OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, CRIS, etc.);
- Increasing PID adoption in relevant sources;
- Making visible which interventions are needed in relevant sources;
- Supporting the transition from closed to open research information.

Based on your responses, in the workshop (Dec 15) we will prioritize the use cases, identify the relevant metadata types and associated PIDs, and discuss what quality aspects (completeness, accuracy, up-to-date-ness) are most important for these use cases.

1. Your organization:

2. Your role in your organization:

Section 2 - Your use case

Please answer the questions below for a specific use case for your organization. If you'd like to provide additional use cases (1-3 per organization), you can reply to the survey multiple times.

3. Describe your use case in one sentence:
(see the accompanying email for more information)

4. What category does this use case fall into? (multiple answers allowed):

- Reporting
- Evaluation and assessment
- Analysis
- Archiving, storage and sharing
- Information and dissemination

- Other:

Section 3 - Your workflow

The 5 questions below invite you to describe the (current or envisioned) workflow for your use case in more detail. These questions are optional, but will help us in mapping use cases. Brief answers (bullets) are fine!

5. Workflow part 1: Who is involved in this use case?
(what role(s) within your organization)

6. Workflow part 2: What information do you need?
(what information on research outputs, activities etc)

7. Workflow part 3: Where and how do you get the data?
(what systems/platforms do you use / want to use to collect the data)

8. Workflow part 4: How do you process the data?
(what systems/tools/platforms do you use to process the data, and what does that processing look like?)

9. Workflow part 5: What is the end product and goal?
(what systems/tools/platforms do you use to process the data, and what does that processing look like)

Section 4 - Metadata and metadata quality

10. What metadata and PIDs are relevant for your use case?:

11. What category does this use case fall into? (multiple answers allowed):

- Reporting
- Evaluation and assessment
- Analysis
- Archiving, storage and sharing
- Information and dissemination

Other:

12. Where is open metadata limited / limiting?:

13. Where is data quality of open metadata a problem?:

Section 5 - Additional comments

14. Any additional comments?:

APPENDIX 2 - USE CASE WORKFLOWS

1. What information do you need?

- Correct open access status in Unpaywall

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- Institutions,
- Unpaywall
- DOAJ
- Crossref

3. How do you process the data?

- datahub (Qlik BI platform)

4. What is the end product?

- Yearly UNL Open Access Monitor, send by UNL to government and shared publicly.

A - Automated, reproducible and correct open access monitor based on open metadata.

1. What information do you need?

- Metadata on research outputs (articles).
- In the future we would like to expand to other research outputs as well.

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- Crossref; UnPaywall, ISAAC, MyZonMw, OpenAlex are currently used.

3. How do you process the data?

- APIs
- Google Script (Javascript)
- Excel.
- The use case is around enhancing our automation processes and internal reporting mechanisms (dashboarding)

4. What is the end product?

- A fully automated reporting tool for NWO and ZonMw publication outputs,
- For compliance (spot) checks, monitoring publication behaviour; information about use of R&P deals, etc.

B - Open Access monitoring based on open metadata

1. What information do you need?

- Bibliographic metadata of publications and other research outputs

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- Currently using Web of Science.
- We would like to switch to Crossref and/or OpenAlex.

3. How do you process the data?

- Ingesting data into CRIS system (Converis)

4. What is the end product?

- Complete high-quality data in our CRIS system.
- This data will then feed into SEP analyses and analyses of the publishing behavior of our academic staff.

C - Using open research information to fill CRIS system

1. What information do you need?

- Which research output belongs to Maastricht University
- Rich metadata (PIDs)

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- Currently: WoS, Scopus en PubMed.
- We tested OpenAlex but it is not yet good enough.

3. How do you process the data?

- Powershell scripts for extracting the data from sources,
- Storage in SQL database
- Bulk import into CRIS using XML files

4. What is the end product?

- CRIS filled with UM research output that is relevant for the following goals:
- Reporting, visualisation on the portal, self-evaluation for the SEP and grant proposals.

D - Bulk import of research output into CRIS

1. What information do you need?

- Which datasets belong to the UM and who produced them

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- DataCite

3. How do you process the data?

- Powershell scripts
- SQL database
- XML import into CRIS system

4. What is the end product?

- We would like to archive metadata of relevant UM datasets into our CRIS so that they become visible on the portal and can be used in (self-)evaluations

E - Bulk Import of datasets into CRIS

1. What information do you need?

- bibliographic information incl authors, ORCIDs, DOI's, journal names, ISSNs, article titles, publication dates

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- Scopus
- WoS

3. How do you process the data?

- Search alerts in the systems on affiliation

4. What is the end product?

- Well populated CRIS to support management and evaluations and populate repository, also for matching full text the share Open Access (Taverne)

F - Populating CRIS with institution's article output

1. What information do you need?

- depending on project: affiliations, authors, author roles, field of research, citations, mentions, funding, etc

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- CRIS (Pure)
- OpenAlex
- OpenAIRE Graph
- Altmetric,
- Overton

3. How do you process the data?

- Powerbi (M scripting)
- Python scripts

4. What is the end product?

- Dashboard for faculty/department management, policy officers

G - Linking data from multiple sources

1. What information do you need?

- Specifically: the RAID

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- Pure,
- Journal Software,
- LMS,
- Contract Management Database

3. How do you process the data?

- Pure

4. What is the end product?

- To be able to track research projects, those involved and their outcomes.

H - Implement a mature PID strategy

1. What information do you need?

- Basic publication metadata
- Citation impact metrics (total citations, FWCI)
- Subject classification
- Open access status.

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- OpenAlex

3. How do you process the data?

- Data cleaning (deduplication and harmonization),
- Enrichment with data from Pure

4. What is the end product?

- A dashboard with up-to-date insights about the publication profile of faculties and institutes

I - Provide insights to faculties about their research publication profile

1. What information do you need?

- Projects, awarded euros and resulting publications,
- Related research subjects in which Dutch universities have participated.

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- CORDIS
- NWO

3. How do you process the data?

- Backfilling, deduplication, harmonization, instrument type classification, enrichment with data from the finance department

4. What is the end product?

- Dashboard with up-to-date insights about the funding performance of the university.

J - Benchmark university's performance in acquiring 2nd and 3rd funding streams

1. What information do you need?

- DOIs, ISSNs, cited references, open access status, deal information, APC costs, corresponding author information

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- UKBsis, Unpaywall, Crossref, Web of Science, OpenAlex

3. How do you process the data?

- Powershell scripts
- SQL database

4. What is the end product?

- Evaluate the deals

K - Collection evaluation by integrating deal information with OA status and APC costs

1. What information do you need?

- School of Business & Economics uses the information in the JCR to assess possible candidates for employment or promotion

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- JCR - Web of science/Clarivate

3. How do you process the data?

- unknown (not personally involved)

4. What is the end product?

- A ranking of possible candidates

L - Providing alternatives for JCR and specifically AIP

1. What information do you need?

- Affiliation, country and organization type of co-authors

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- WoS
- Scopus
- OpenAlex
- CRIS

3. How do you process the data?

- not known

4. What is the end product?

- information for research directors, research programmers, internationalisation policy officers to evaluate international relations

M - Mapping research collaborations

Utrecht
University

1. What information do you need?

- Information regarding the role of corresponding author

2. Where and how do you get the data?

- OpenAlex,
- Scopus,
- publisher reports
- (OpenAire doesn't provide corresponding author info)

3. How do you process the data?

- Qlik datawarehouse

4. What is the end product?

- Reports
- Analyses
- Calculations.

N - Availability of corresponding author information (for OA costs, missed OA, etc)

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